

Hooman – An Online Dating Website

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Abstract:- In society there are two types of people some are introverts and extroverts. Introverts prefer not to be socialized much and could be shy to talk to people, but in the end, we are all humans we all need someone to be with not to be lonely, so at a point in their life they need a mate to live with, so they could date or marry someone, some of the introverts don't know how to start a conversation even if they do most of the time they would feel awkward when having a conversation, to overcome this new advanced series of features have been added. Using a profile matcher with a series of questions shows what would be their personality and by grading them, users who have the same grades will be matched, this would make it easier for people to get connected with one another because they might have the same hobbies and same interests, so the bonding experience is easy, as an advanced feature, having a horoscope matcher is very valuable for the people in Asia, especially in Sri Lanka because of the culture. Here you need to give the image of the horoscope and it automatically matches with others and gives suggestions, an intelligent message supporter as a feature, some introverts have no idea what they have to say if another person is texting them, so using this intelligent message supporter we suggest what are the responses that user can give to the other person. Video games tend to attract more people just because they are interactive and fun and eventful, so a video game is perfect to predict the strengths and weaknesses of the player in order to give the player's partner an idea about them.

Keywords:- Introverts, Profile Matcher, Horoscope Matcher, Intelligent Message Supporter, Video Game.

I. INTRODUCTION

When it comes to online dating, the person we like can be a psychopath or worse even though from the first impression to be the most honest and innocent person. But if we can get to know this person to some extent the risks can be mitigated, so using some advanced features with dating sites will help users to be more careful and to pick a decent

person to spend the rest of their life, such as having a personality test using an algorithm, the system calculates the personality of the user and suggests mutual users same as the user's personality, but this is not enough if the users are more matured with the system and found a good match for their next step would be the marriage or some of the people start their relationship by matching horoscopes this is mostly happening in Sri Lanka because we have a culture to maintain and most family members approve the partner only if the horoscope gets matched. So as our second feature we can use a horoscope matching feature, but this is not enough to get to know one another because the horoscope doesn't say anything about what kind of a person they are, but what if they could know what the strengths and weaknesses are of each other in a romantic relationship, this way they can get an idea about each other. A game will analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the player. Finally, an intelligent chat service most introverts need to be trained before talking to people because most of them don't know how to respond to other people's texts so the intelligent message supporter gives them suggestions from previous chats, if a similar conversation happened before then this chatbot gives what to say, so you can select it and send it. Regarding the game, two game levels have been developed where each level predicts a strength or a weakness. In level one, the listening skill of the player will be predicted. In level one player must navigate through a maze with the help of audio clips [6][7]. There are invisible score points inside the maze if the player goes along the correct path according to the audio clips score points will be added to the score and there are penalty points that will be used to deduct the score points of the player if they went off course. A Machine Learning model will help to predict the strengths and weaknesses of the player. The second level is somewhat trickier because it measures problem-solving skills. It's a puzzle-solving game and this level will improve and predict the user's problem-solving skills. According to Mayer and Wittrock (1996, 2006) [5], there are a few characteristics of problem-solving.

- 1) It is a cognitive process.
- 2) It is goal oriented.
- 3) Complexity (and hence difficulty) of the problem depends on one's current knowledge and skills. and since

puzzle games have these characteristics and can tap into multiple cognitive abilities [8] puzzle games can be used to measure and improve problem-solving skills of a player.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over time there are many features that have come up with dating platforms and the community also talked about developing some advanced features, but these were harder to do when we are talking about Tinder, they just give photos of people to swipe left or right if they like them. This was not an accurate approach to matching someone. When it comes to online dating there is a saying, “you have to kiss a lot of frogs to find a prince”. Meeting someone online is fundamentally different than meeting someone in real life [1]. Therefore, having a personality test describes more about the user to the system then using machine learning we can suggest what are the best matches for them so the user can see only people who have similar personalities just like them which makes it more exciting. If the user trusts the system, then the user will not be afraid and move on with the date. When it comes to matching people with other people within Sri Lanka or within South Asia horoscope can play a main role but this feature is not implemented on any dating website because people had not thought to a greater extent than people have proposal matching websites[5] but you need to have a partner to match your proposal this is always not easy so if we use those implementations in a dating website people can use their horoscopes and match it with the person who they got suggested with if it is and if the user likes the matched person, then they can even build up a future without hesitating. This horoscope matching is included in our system, and it is consulted and instructed to be made by a real astrologer because most of the time online horoscope matching could be wrong and end up in failed marriages [2].

III. METHODOLOGY

To implement this we used multiple number of data sets because each of these systems are different from each other and only two of them need to have data sets that would be the intelligent chat bot and “profile suggesting” components, both these data sets were gained from Kaggle, one dataset is used to analyze the conversations of people in movies and if the models were trained with them then the model learns how to think like a normal human, the main purpose is to get information about the user and suggest the best match possible for them therefore when it comes to horoscope matching all need to be researched from many articles and find the patterns in them and understand how the concept works this was done by learning from astrologer to match the patterns and this “information” is made by the researcher himself and two array sets have been used to train the gaming model to get the relationship between the score of the game (1st array set - 5, 10, 15, ...) and a value that need to be given (2nd array set - 0, 0, 1, 1, ...) which is between 0 and 1.

Fig.1. overall diagram

Intelligent Message Supporter. In the conversational dataset, responses are grouped as sender and receiver removing the stop words and making a bag of words so the unique and meaningful words are in that bag so the response is generated from this bag of words, definitely, these sentences are not going to make any sense because they cannot be grammatically correct since there are no stop words and might not make any sense either, because processing sentences, so while we are doing feature engineering, we make two arrays to store these sender and responder values after that using seq2seq model and LSTM[1] we make a relationship between these two groups and categorical cross entropy as the loss function, therefore, it will calculate how bad the guess is and give it to the optimizer Adam so it can make a better prediction for the next prediction. This is the machine learning model training process, now this model is stored in the frontend and when the user types in the chat the text passes into the Machine Learning model and predicts what would be the response, and using the tokenization method, the system tokenizes the text, so it has a numerical value so it's easier to find the similar sentences which have the same words and token values as the response, this can be a range of words and limited it to a few sentences these stored responses are used by the users who used the chat earlier. Seq2seq problems are a special class of Sequence modeling problems, both these problems are regarding input and output of sequences. Specially Encoder- Decoder models were used to solve Seq2Seq problems. For the encoder we pass the input sequence according to this scenario we pass the text which user types as the message, from the encoder it generates a vector, this is a collection of tokens and this is always fixed length this is called as ‘context vector’ this holds the whole meaning of the sentence as a vector, this vector is making the decoder easier to make the accurate predictions. The decoder reads this vector and goes from each token to token and targets the sequence token by token [2].

Fig.2. Basic process structure in Intelligent Message Supporter (Chatbot)

```

Model: "sequential"
-----
Layer (type)                Output Shape                Param #
-----
dense (Dense)                (None, 128)                 21376
dropout (Dropout)            (None, 128)                 0
dense_1 (Dense)              (None, 64)                  8256
dropout_1 (Dropout)          (None, 64)                  0
dense_2 (Dense)              (None, 21)                  1365
-----
Total params: 30,997
Trainable params: 30,997
Non-trainable params: 0
  
```

Fig.3. Summary of the model

Profile Verification System. A Convolutional Neural network, which is one of the main image processing models used in neural networks has been trained in identifying characteristics of images related to face attributes. As per image preprocessing, all the images are converted to grayscale to reduce the noise of the images. The following classifications were conducted by processing images using CNN's. Four models have been built using CNN in order to classify age, gender, hair, and nose. Based on the model and its classification accuracy, convolution layers were used with an activation function. The dense layer of the output layer has a softmax activation function according to categories that needs to be classified by the model.

```

In [5]: checkpoint = ModelCheckpoint('models/2_0/model_{epoch:03d}.model', monitor='val_loss', verbose=0, save_best_only=True, mode='auto')
history = model.fit(train_data, train_target, epochs=5, callbacks=[checkpoint], validation_split=0.1)
history = model.evaluate(train_data, train_target, epochs=5, callbacks=[checkpoint], verbose=1)

Epoch 1/5 [====...] - 474 0s - loss: 0.9131 - accuracy: 0.9921000 - tensorboard: assets written to: models/2_0
Epoch 2/5 [====...] - 474 0s - loss: 0.0000e+00 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0000e+00 - val_accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 3/5 [====...] - 474 0s - loss: 0.0000e+00 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0000e+00 - val_accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 4/5 [====...] - 474 0s - loss: 0.0000e+00 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0000e+00 - val_accuracy: 1.0000
Epoch 5/5 [====...] - 474 0s - loss: 0.0000e+00 - accuracy: 1.0000 - val_loss: 0.0000e+00 - val_accuracy: 1.0000
  
```

Fig.4. Model Training in the Profile Verification System

A training test split is used to sample the training dataset against the test data set. Model checkpoint has been used to save the best model with the highest accuracies.

Horoscope Matching System Users must upload an image of their horoscope. Using image processing, The

main technologies that are used to build this component are image processing and CNN (Convolutional Natural Network) which are used for building deep learning models. This CNN behaves like a human brain when it is identifying images [10],[11]. When we use this CNN, it needs a data set to train the Machine Learning model to identify the combinations between horoscopes since there were no found data for this purpose to be found on the internet this data was made by the researcher himself with the help of a professional Astrologer. There are 12 astrological signs and this astrological sign when we are writing in Sinhala it can be different in many ways it changes from person to person therefore only from one astrological sign researcher took 250 to 300 images to train what is the written name looks like to train the model to capture the image using CNN so that model knows exactly what the astrological sign is accurately. So, it has a collective knowledge of around more than 3000 images, so the model gets the value correct way [14]. Now for the Machine Learning algorithm this component passes the Astrological sign that's detected and do the prediction using this method matching the horoscope is promising and the results are very accurate also since this needs to improve much more later as for the start this is a very good start and a very good method to match horoscopes, the accuracy of the Machine Learning model is high more like 85% as shown in the Fig 4), when considering accuracy this is a good rate

Fig.5. Model training Diagram

```

Classifier
Epoch 92/100 [====...] - 4s 157ms/step - loss: 1.2308 - accuracy: 0.5986
Epoch 93/100 [====...] - 4s 155ms/step - loss: 1.0945 - accuracy: 0.6176
Epoch 94/100 [====...] - 4s 149ms/step - loss: 1.0594 - accuracy: 0.6494
Epoch 95/100 [====...] - 4s 150ms/step - loss: 1.1574 - accuracy: 0.6217
Epoch 96/100 [====...] - 4s 157ms/step - loss: 1.1287 - accuracy: 0.6238
Epoch 97/100 [====...] - 4s 168ms/step - loss: 1.0279 - accuracy: 0.6535
Epoch 98/100 [====...] - 5s 169ms/step - loss: 1.1463 - accuracy: 0.6384
Epoch 99/100 [====...] - 4s 168ms/step - loss: 1.0799 - accuracy: 0.6560
Epoch 100/100 [====...] - 4s 157ms/step - loss: 1.0716 - accuracy: 0.6274
Test Score = 0.576939582824787
Test Accuracy = 0.8566787419319153
Process finished with exit code 0
  
```

Fig.6. Model training in Horoscope Matching Component

After training is finished Machine Learning model needs to be deployed to the backend so from the frontend image is passed to the backend of our system as a POST

request through the API. Earlier CNN was used to process the dataof the image and the accuracy of the image detection washigh from that but before moving on to the Machine Learning model Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is used to detect the image’s data, to process the image and get the data. Todo this we have used 550 images to train the model, but the accuracy of the result is very poor (accuracy of 34Becauseof that we moved on to CNN, OCR process is done by the predefined model itself, but this CNN model is made by the researcher himself.

Strength and Weakness finder (Game) Mainly used lo- gistic regression to implement this component. To reduce codecomplexity (Unity accesses the ONNX model as an asset so there is no need for hard coding in unity). Especially in a videogame, we should maintain less code complexity because it willcause GPU CPU to be in high usage and video games use GPU and CPU heavily so code complexity will affect GPU and CPU as a result it will affect the game performance asthe game grows and becomes more complex with the future works. We use previously trained data (an array set of the score given by each level and an array for results according to the score) which will lead to more accurate results (accuracy- 0.89) than not using Machine Learning. For example, if we use if-else we will only know if the player has good listening skills or poor listening skills. If we want to get the percentage of the listening skill, we have to write more code which will lead to more complexity of the game (as mentioned above). It is better to use a Machine Learning algorithm to predict the player’s strengths and weaknesses which was trained using training data to get a more accurate result with the percentage of the listening skill because even if the player got the full score, it doesn’t mean that the player has the best listningskill so prediction using previously trained data is the best option here. There are two levels in this game for the second level we mainly focus on how good the user is when it comes to solving problems, for this purpose a jigsaw puzzle is used, When the player solves the puzzle and if they complete the puzzle with extra time left on the timer, they get extra points but if they take longer to complete the puzzle than the given time a penalty will impose. So, the result that goes into the system for the Machine Learning model will be reduced. And for every correct placement, the game score will be increased.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It’s a highly advanced system and much harder to maneuversince we have to predict everything that user does when they logged into the system, there is always a probability the rate ofbeing successful, and models need to be trained more, that’s what we have found so far but the probability of the success rate is high since we use actual conversations of people and model prediction is most of the time suggests pretty much the correct reply that we need to use for but the accuracy is not much likable and need to develop a lot more than right now.

Fig.7. Chat screen of the Intelligent Message Supporter

Fig.8. Profile Verification System result interface

HOROSCOPE MATCHING

compatible

Fig.9. Horoscope matching result

Fig.10. Gamification interface

So, what we really need to work on more right now isnot about the optimizers or the loss function but the data preprocessing part since this is a product that needs to be with people to help get their shyness and unfamiliarity about how to talk. The chatbot can help them a lot

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Since this model is deployed with the website it will learn new words, new sentences and everything but that's not enough, need to monitor how regularly people use this model and the answers it suggests to them if they are using it more often then it's great but what if the suggestions are not suitable at all, so we have to monitor it, by collecting the data that users used to chat with each other, more like chats people are having so we can detect what are the areas that they are more commonly focused on and if that area needs to have an improvement focusing on that area can improve the chatbot a lot. Always this needs to be more focused on the empathy side because all humans need to be treated nicely and gently. As for the game component, it can,

- 1) Use more levels to get more strengths or weaknesses of the player
- 2) We can use this method to get not only strengths and weaknesses but also personality traits too.

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